

Bilingualism: A Boon and a Ladder to Success

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Abstract

The present study focusses on writer's personal experience with students. Second language or multi language learning has become a necessity of present time. But in Graduation, College Students are not aware with this fact and reality. Their first language is such an integral part of their speaking and thinking that they even can't write a basic article without any help. So, the paper suggests them utility of bilingualism and some suggestions how they can learn second language.

Key Words:

Acquisition, Achieves, Fluency, Curriculum, Multilingualism.

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“The more languages you know, the more you are human”

Introduction

Everyone loves and adores his mother tongue, because all their milestones from childhood to adulthood have been crossed in their mother tongue. It can be Hindi or any regional language because India has many regional languages. But as the fast changing scenario, we need to improve and change ourselves globally and internationally. Although our mother tongue is like blood flowing in our veins, but we need to be bilingual to progress and upgrade ourselves. We started celebrating English Language Day on 23 April every year, not because we are aping America or Britain, but English has become the Franca Lingua of our life. Compare two persons getting a similar education from similar institute still they get different jobs; one higher and other lesser, just because the other can't communicate confidently in English. English in the present scenario is a deciding factor of selecting candidature for jobs as well as admissions and other

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academic and professional activities. Bilingualism creates a creativity factor and develops thinking as well. We learn vocabulary which gives opportunity to think widely and express accurately and exactly. As there are many expressions and feelings which can easily be explained in English other than mother tongue whatever it is.

English Language Day was first time declared and celebrated in 2010 by UNO as this is William Shakespeare's birthday also. English was the language of only 3 tribes 1500 years before, but now it has become an official language of nearly 2 billion people. Nearly 70 countries are working and speaking in English with two major variants: British and American and now one less common is Australian.

Multinational culture has made English a cup of tea for everyone, whether a computer operator or a CEO of a company. These day's developments in business, jobs, higher studies and even day to day conversation is based on fluency and mastery over English. Hindi

or other regional languages which play as mother tongue are in our blood obviously. We think, eat, learn and express in them spontaneously, but now the need is to make English our cup of Tea.

Focus of the Study

In this chapter, my focus is on bilingualism or second language acquisition. Bilingualism actually means a group of persons who possess knowledge of one more language other than their mother tongue. Not only knowledge, but they have to be fluent in speaking and accurately in writing. They can produce a complete meaningful utterance in their second language. Second language acquisition also covers a wide range of social and cultural aspects of language related to learner's acquisition and competence. There are many degrees of bilingualism as native like proficiency in both languages is rare. Naturally, everyone has a 'dominant' language which is usually his mother tongue, but here the focus is on adopting second language without any flaws and with complete mastery.

Bilingualism and its Need

We normally define bilingualism as having the ability to speak in two or more than two languages with the flow and without flaws. In many countries other than India a majority of the population is either multilingual or bilingual. And above to that countries like France still progressing and developing day by day with their monolinguality. But in today's world, becoming bilingual is a necessity if you want to cross the borders and want to be a voracious reader. There are several ways to bring up, by which we can try to adopt more than one language:

Parents normally follow one language pattern as they speak their native language and comfortable in that only. This makes parents, child bondage more connected but bilingualism always gives them a reason to connect with others. Parents should themselves give their children a chance and exposure for that. I have seen NRI's talking in Hindi to their children at home, but they learn a second language at Day care center, schools, Institutes fluently.

This is called a minority language pattern. Children receive exposure from outside and become versatile. Otherwise adaptation of second languages at

maturity level produces barriers of fluency, pronunciation and limitations of vocabulary. Although it is claimed that second language comes automatically with the use and atmosphere, but this is not true and perfect. Second language acquisition should start from childhood only because children are capable of learning one or more language from beginning and they can differentiate when and with whom to speak which language. This is practically experienced and tested formula. Researches show that bilingual students acquire language better than monolingual children. They may start speaking a litter delayed, but once they start, they will surpass monolingual peers.

Advantages of Bilingualism:

“Languages is the archives of history”

RW Emerson rightly said this. Researches show that learning a foreign language takes time and dedication, but it is mandatory to be versatile in a second language. In the present era of globalization, one need not to be dependent on a certain country or region as language sometimes plays a great barrier. I personally experience that even if many of the locals know, understand

and can speak in your language, they pretend not to understand and will only reply in their native language. Even if you manage anyhow, you will not be able to cope with their culture, thinking and proper communication.

Presently, work culture also demands bilingualism as outsourcing talent and technology demand regular contact with speakers of different and foreign languages. It will help to negotiate, finding new job opportunities, getting promotions, pay hikes and visiting and working in different countries. Similarly, this rule applies to studies and researches. I have personally experienced students coming and going to US, UK, Germany, Netherlands and Switzerland for technical up gradation and higher education. But it has become possible only because of their adaptation of second language other than their Mother Tongue from the beginning of their studies or rather since they started speaking. Even L₁ and L₂ sometimes are not the complete package. Suppose you are studying or going to France for some travel or business purpose you have to learn some French also as they are very particular about their Mother Tongue. Many writers

and Thinkers believe that for language learning, only sky is the limit.

Conclusions and Recommendations

So, if we turn the pages of literature we will find that great thinkers, writers and many successful people keep on learning languages here and after. It may be love for any religion, culture, communication with foreigners, music, and singing and blab blab. But after research and study the most cognitive advantages, I come to know:

- Personality development and multi-tasking.
- Works as memory booster and make brain disorders away.
- Better decision making a wider perspective of life.
- Enriched vocabulary gives a great perspective to express oneself.

Bilingualism does not mean to start speaking a second language without knowing its grammar, construction, structures and correct use of words. People normally attend short term courses and cram sentences, expression and produce it as and when needed. This is the worst way of learning a language. I

personally teach the students coming from rural or semi urban background whose MT is normally Hindi, that too is not pure and correct but full of locate effects and accents. Their medium of instruction at school level is Hindi or English that too is not flawless. So, it is a hard nut to crack to make them speak, learn and write correct English (SLL). They are eager to take English as a subject, but they cram their answers, write in cracked and incorrect English but fluent in speaking is far far away.

Some Tasks to Adopt for Bilingualism

Learners who study with the aim of better understanding, speaking, learning, writing can only adapt second language. Role of parents, teachers, family and society is also important because language learning also need a lot of patience and motivation. Some easy to pick exercises which really works unintentionally are:

- Reading, Reading and Reading in the second language.
- Listening and watching movies, programmes and songs of second language.
- Language Labs, Club and groups also work well.

- Above all, always set an aim to achieve that too a realistic one. Suppose you decide to learn 25 words daily, learn them by hook or crook.
- Last but not the least, always use the words, sentences you have

learned by far because practical experience is always best.

The more we speak, the more we learn, keep this in mind and anyone can go for second language leaning any time. The key to success of bilingualism is continuous learning and improving by mistakes.

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